

British Broadcasting Corporation

The Digital Media Initiative

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Table of Contents- Lingyi Meng

Table of Contents- Lingyi Meng	1
1.0 Introduction - Qiyuan Tian	3
2.0 Background - Qiyuan Tian	4
3.0 Project Objectives - Lloyd Thomas Wood IV	5
3.1 Siemens IT Solutions and Services DMI Objectives	6
3.2 BBC DMI In-House Objectives	7
3.3 Real Life Implications	8
4.0 Success factors - Lloyd Thomas Wood IV	9
4.1 Cancelling Siemens Contact	9
4.2 DMI Governance	10
5.0 Failure Factors - Enrico Vallejos	11
5.1 Project Management	11
5.1.1. Overall ineffectiveness of project leadership	11
5.1.2. Business requirements of the project was poorly defined.	12
5.2 Project Risk Management	12
5.2.1. Poorly planned risk management in an application development project	12
5.2.2. Risk assessment was insufficient during procurement process	13
5.2.3. Insufficient risk management and contingency plan for project resources	13
5.3. Project Communications Management	14
5.3.1. Reporting arrangements were not sufficient for the project	14
5.4 Project Stakeholder Management	15
5.4.1. Decrease of stakeholder confidence in the project	15
6.0 Lessons Learned - Lingyi Meng	15
Phase I: Initiation	15
Phase II: Planning	16
Phase III: Execution	17
Phase IV: Delivery	18
7.0 Recommendation- Lingyi Meng	18
7.1 Professional Manager Team	18
7.2 Information Gathering In Advance	18
7.3 Learn From History	19
7.4 Enforce Learning Process	19
7.5 Manage Agile PM Methods	20
7.6 Make a Planning Checklist for project plan	20
8.0 Conclusion - Sarath Laghumarapu	21

Appendix

24

References Used: - Sarath

28

1.0 Introduction - Qiyuan Tian

The British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) is one of the world's oldest and most powerful media production and broadcasting organization. Since 1992, BBC has created plenty of media archive materials, which increased the storage burden and declined the efficiency to create new materials. As a result, British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) decided to initiate the "Digital Media Initiative" (DMI) in 2008 to reform the traditional way of digital content delivery.

Digital Media Initiative (DMI) is a business transformation program with technology innovation, aiming to better manage and integrate archive materials, as well as allows BBC staff to access the entire archive from their computers, doing away with the need for audio and video tapes. The Program is supported by a technology system binding together production (where users manage the recreation of media content and need the latest creative digital media tools) and archiving (where users manage data storage, indexing and retrieval and require more traditional Information Technology and tools).

The main delivery and contents of DMI program can be expressed as follows:

- A data management system, including a structured format for data, and a catalogue database that listed all archived projects and content.
- A digital archive to store all new BBC content
- Production tools, for example desktop editing tools
- Common enterprise services underpinning the above

In addition to technology delivery part, DMI also deliver a standard set of business process across the BBC, which required a significant change in operational and cultural ways of working^[12].

2.0 Background - Qiyuan Tian

In order to improve the efficiency and better management the storage way of archive materials, the BBC set up Digital Media Initiative (DMI) program. The estimated gross cost of program delivery and implementation to the end of March 2017 is £133.6 million. However, due to some factors, the DMI project was finally abandoned in May 2013. The time line of DMI program (from initiation to failure) can be seen in Appendix (Figure 1)^[11].

In March 2007, the Finance Committee approved budget of £6.6 million for the detailed design of DMI, and in January 2008, the BBC Trust approved program with budget of £82 million. In February 2008, the BBC entered into an agreement with Siemens to deliver DMI without going through a formal tender process. And awarded Siemens £79 million fixed prize contract to design and deliver the system. Following a series of delivery delays, the BBC and Siemens reached a mutual agreement to terminate the DMI contract in 2009.

In June 2010, an agreement on a revised DMI was finally reached between the BBC and the Trust. And BBC approved revised investment case for a wider roll-out with a revised budget £133.6 million. At the meantime, the DMI implementation was under the control of the BBC

with third parties contracted to provide specific deliverables or resources under the direction of the BBC.

Over the course of 2012, it became clear to the BBC and the Trust that there were significant problems with the delivery of DMI. In February 2012, the project management office graded the status of DMI as red and suggested the BBC finance committee consider stopping or re-evaluating the program. And in September 2012, the Trust FC requested that any amended proposal for the future of DMI be put before them for consideration^[12].

By the end of 2012, BBC completed its fundamental review of DMI and concluded that DMI would not deliver the BBC's future business needs for digital, tapeless production, at which point the decision was made to stop the program and write down the asset value. In May 2013, Sadly the warnings turned out to have merit as the failure to deliver a working system resulted in the project being abandoned.

3.0 Project Objectives - Lloyd Thomas Wood IV

The Objectives for the BBC Digital Media Initiative (DMI) were first introduced with Siemens IT Solutions and Services (Siemens) and then were redefined by BBC Trust, when the DMI project was brought in house after cancelling the contract with Siemens.

3.1 Siemens IT Solutions and Services DMI Objectives

The BBC initially awarded the DMI project to Siemens in 2008 to develop and implement^[2]. Based on the Siemens Press Release from April 2008 the goal was to allow for “faster programme making, improved opportunities for collaborative working and a reduction in total production costs through the introduction of end-to-end tapeless workflows”^[2]. Based on this goal, Siemens’ implementation of the DMI would create a:

- “Digital library - provides core management of all video, audio and images created by the Corporation and its supplies, together with its associated information
- Work-in-progress production system - allows producers to search, view, sort, storyboard and store work-in-progress content
- Craft edit integration - enables the tapeless transfer of browse and broadcast quality content and its associated metadata from the work-in-progress environment to a mix of Avid and Apple non-linear editing systems for finishing
- Portal solution - custom designed user interface providing users with secure access to the functionality provided by the underlying solutions
- Enterprise services - to manage the effective movement of media essence across the network and allow content to be transformed into the required formats
- Bundle and package - to support the sharing of essence and metadata across platforms and with any requesting system”^[2].

3.2 BBC DMI In-House Objectives

When the project with Siemens was cancelled in 2009^[12], the objectives were redefined by the BBC Trust. The purpose for the DMI development was to create a custom program, since available products did not have the capabilities to share digital files that were archived and in production^[3]. The objectives for the BBC DMI, were not explicitly stated like Siemens' objectives, but they were envisioned by the BBC Trust to allow for “strategic investment in infrastructure, people and production processes that supported both the BBC’s creative vision and its technology strategy to standardise the production, storage and use of digital content across TV, radio, and online”^[12]. It was the goal of the BBC Trust that DMI would be comprised of the following:

- “A data management system, including a structured format for data, and a catalogue database that listed all archived projects and content
- A digital archive to store all new BBC content
- Production tools, i.e. desktop editing tools
- Common enterprise services underpinning the above”^[12].

The DMI goal to change the way things operated within the BBC to allow for a more modernized and seamless process in dealing with video management^[1]. The overall objective of creating a digital platform to create, develop, edit and share digital media remained relatively the same with the project transfer from Siemens to the BBC in-house team.

3.3 Real Life Implications

There are a couple real life implications for the BBC DMI project that could have been achieved by the intended objectives of both the Siemens and BBC in-house initiative. First is the ability for the BBC to move into a more 21st century video creation and storage program. By having a digital based storage program, the BBC employees would be able to access their vast collection of data from any workstation within the organization. Having a centralized platform for video creation and storage digitized; would allow for BBC staff to seamlessly share, upload, and manage video data.

Another real life implication had this project been successfully completed is providing greater productivity among BBC employees. Employees would be able to access the files they needed almost instantaneously, instead of having to search a physical archive room or requesting the files from the archives if they themselves did not go the archive.

One digital media solutions that has proven to be successful is the implementation of NETApp storage solution. This digital media storage systems has been utilized by many different entertainment industries and news broadcasting corporations such as, CBS, Comcast, and Sky News^[6]. One success story in particular is Evergreen Films, which is a production company, that covers all aspects of film development^[7]. While in the entertainment industry, Evergreen Films and the BBC were looking for similar solutions when it comes to video data storage, editing and sharing, Evergreen Films indicated that their “IT needs, especially on the data storage side, have grown exponentially [in recent years]”^[7]. Evergreen Films was able to implement NetApp

E-series storage to handle the vast amount of data that the company produces and handles on a regular basis^[7]. The NetApp E-Series would allow for the following advances in data storage and management:

- “Extreme bandwidth and throughput performance that could meet Evergreen’s real-time playback needs
- Excellent system stability, reliability, and agility, especially for sustained or varied workflows
- Economical pricing for an enterprise-class storage system of its type.”^[7]

Not only was Evergreen Films able to get the data storage and management system that fulfilled their needs, it was also able to save them money in the long run. With their previous system, playback of video cost “\$5 per gigabyte, NetApp has set a new aggressive price bar: Enterprise storage suited for video playback for well under \$1 per gigabyte”^[7], thus saving a significant amount of money for Evergreen Films.

4.0 Success factors - Lloyd Thomas Wood IV

While the project overall was cancelled in May 2013 and can be considered a failure, since it was not completed, there are some success factors with this IT project implementation.

4.1 Cancelling Siemens Contact

One action that can be considered a success with this IT project implementation was the termination of the Siemens contract to create the DMI for BBC. The Siemens contract was granted in February 2008, but by July 2009 it was terminated^[4]. The BBC terminated the

contract with Siemens because “Siemens failed to meet the desired deadline for completing the project, causing lesser savings than anticipated”^[5]. The cancellation of the Siemens contract can be seen as a success in that the BBC recognized that Siemens was not reaching the intended deadlines and it was costing the organization more money than necessary. It would be beneficial for other organizations to learn from this example that if a group or team is not meeting the outlined objectives and deadlines, it is good to reconsider the contract at hand. However, by the termination of the Siemens contract, the BBC had already lost £38.4 million^[5].

4.2 DMI Governance

Another success of the BBC DMI project was the organization and structure of meetings that were held by the stakeholders of the project. Figure 2 in the Appendix outlines the structures and frequency as reported in PWC’s “BBC Digital Media Initiative Review of the BBC’s Management of DMI”^[12]. Having this outline of meeting structures for the different groups for the BBC DMI project could be viewed as a success because there was an organizational structure in place to ensure the project was meeting the designated objectives. However, looking at the number of groups that were meeting and the frequency of the meetings, it is not surprising to find out that so many changes were requested with the requirements^[4]. I think that this BBC DMI project can be viewed as a project with bad stakeholder management, considering all the changes that were requested leading to the project’s cancellation.

5.0 Failure Factors - Enrico Vallejos

5.1 Project Management

5.1.1. Overall ineffectiveness of project leadership

The DMI project leadership structure for the project was not effective in executing the plan for a complex project like the DMI^[12]. First, the BBC did not appoint a single responsible owner of the project to act as the point of accountability and align all elements of the project. Project accountability was divided between the BBC Future Media and Technology Division and the different divisions where the system would be used. The BBC Future Media and Technology Division was responsible for delivering and deploying the system while the different divisions that would use the system were responsible in ensuring that DMI generated the project benefits in their respective unit^[12]. Since there was no single point of accountability of the project, there was a difference of expectations between those developing the system and its intended users. Second, the level of scrutiny in which the project leadership applied for a high value and strategically important project that involved significant risks was insufficient. It was evident that they did not fully understand the extent of the problems the project was facing until only late in the project. Third, key roles in the DMI project leadership team underwent several changes in staffing over a short period of time (see Figure 3)^[11]. This caused a lack of continuity in the knowledge of the project, which resulted in reduced effectiveness of decision-making and confusion due to different approaches to risk management. Finally, there was no steering board to challenge the progress of the project against the agreed quality, time, and cost.

5.1.2. Business requirements of the project was poorly defined.

Instead of focusing on establishing detailed business requirements for the archiving and production components of the system, the project leaders focused on the deployment of the early releases of the system^[12]. The unclear business requirements resulted in delays, procurement problems, and a lack of alignment between the system development and the user requirements of the archiving and production system. When BBC did an internal audit in July 2012, it reported that they did not establish a clear blueprint of how the end-product would look like^[12]. When another audit was done in August 2012, it added that even though the purpose of the archive system was understood, the DMI user requirements were still vague and confusing and the end users were indifferent about using the production tools of the system. In addition, when a technical assessment was done by Accenture during March 2013, BBC was still confused about what components of the system were for^[12].

5.2 Project Risk Management

5.2.1. Poorly planned risk management in an application development project

Since there was no “off-the-shelf” system that was available in the market, BBC needed to develop the system from the scratch. DMI was going to be a large-scale software development project that would encounter several risks^[3]. This is because of the complexities and high degree of interdependency among the different business units and their processes involved. When the project was handled by Siemens, it used the “big-bang” method where the project would release updates for the system in large, “big-bang” releases. BBC did not consider the risk of a

“big-bang” approach as opposed to following a more iterative or agile approach in involving the development, procurement, and integration of different technologies. BBC concluded that the agile software development approach was more effective when the project was brought in-house due to the delays the previous approach caused. There were many interdependencies that exist between the products and components that make up the whole system. If there was no proper planning in terms of risk management against schedule, then a problem or delay in one area will impact the others in a domino effect and will cumulatively impact the whole project.

5.2.2. Risk assessment was insufficient during procurement process

BBC did not go through a formal procurement process to choose a vendor to develop the system^[3]. It is standard practice to hold such a procedure because competition allows the purchaser to compare potential supplier prices and technical proposal, as well as their capability and capacity to deliver the project. Since BBC did not go through a formal procurement process, and chose Siemens, their current supplier of technology management services, the company did not have an up-to-date assessment of Siemen’s capability to deliver the project. The lack of capability to deliver the project was apparent when the project experienced delays during the design phase. During this phase, the project should have completed the specifications on how the DMI system would look and feel like to the users. This delay eventually affected the whole project schedule.

5.2.3. Insufficient risk management and contingency plan for project resources

When BBC took over the project from Siemens because of the delays in the project, BBC’s Future Media and Technology Division, which was also one of the project’s stakeholders,

prepared a contingency plan. They admitted that it was created without a full understanding of the technical and design issues that Siemens encountered. This resulted in a lot of gaps in the skills and knowledge base to deliver the project. To compensate this, BBC had to get recruit or use several third party suppliers to fill the gap, which subsequently affected the project cost. In addition to a lack of an effective contingency plan, risk identification processes were not followed since risk and issue logs were not kept up-to-date.

5.3. Project Communications Management

5.3.1. Reporting arrangements were not sufficient for the project

There was no clear view of the project progress because project team did not provide clear and transparent reports to the stakeholders^[12]. According to their project communications plan, the stakeholders of the project received quarterly reports from the project team. These reports contained a summary of how the project is progressing as well as the ratings of the risk the project may encounter. It was discovered during an audit that there was a six-month gap between a change in risk rating of one of the identified risks and the time it was reported to the stakeholders (see Figure 4)^[11]. The effective decision-making for the project was severely affected because of the inefficiency of the communications delivered by the project team. Another factor on how the reporting affected the execution of the project, project reporting focused on the risks and issues in a technological view, but did not clearly state whether the system could achieve an operational change to BBC's business practices. Aside from that, the timing of the briefings was not consistent and was ad hoc in nature. This resulted in conflicting

views of the project in terms of progress, issues and risks. Reporting on a quarterly basis also means that the reported status of the project lagged the current status of the project.

5.4 Project Stakeholder Management

5.4.1. Decrease of stakeholder confidence in the project

The technical problems and releases not meeting user expectations, which are considered stakeholders in a project, contributed to repeated extensions of the project schedule, which led to the decrease of stakeholder confidence in the reliability of the system. Due to these delays and the increasing demand to have a working system, some users in the production department had to install an alternative system and used it as a stand-alone system. As soon as this happened, users started to question the benefits of the DMI system.

6.0 Lessons Learned - Lingyi Meng

The Project Life Cycle (PLC) is not only an efficient framework to direct a profound way for a team to build projects but also a useful tool for us to analyze what we can learn from a failed project. SDLC distributes the whole project into four core phases: Initiation, Planning, Execution and Delivery^[18].

Phase I: Initiation

BBC DMI requires a clear project objective: Project management is the application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to project activities to meet project requirements^[8]. The original business objective of DMI is to produce new online digital archive and new database as

in-house production tools for BBC. However, the BBC executive has an insufficient grip of the programme because DMI has suffered from a lack of clear and consistent direction concerning business requirements. The major IT project is on the rocks of disagreements between business and IT leaders.

The project should meet users' requirements: Project managers should meet the triple constraint, which includes scope, time and cost goals and also facilitate the entire process to meet the needs and expectation of project users^[4]. Business users of BBC believe that the result of software is not what they wanted because what they need is the off-the-shelf product from Adobe, but DMI finally produced a “rough cut” of video output, leading to many software written off to adjust into customers' needs^[2].

Phase II: Planning

A high-quality plan is a big picture for a project: The project plan should contain clear goals, missions, and objectives together with a general approach to management and technology^[19]. It is evident that the BBC work-plan is not integrated. At least for initial part, the project plan should indicate the way to organize and staff the project in responsibility and accountability. The contractual aspects of BBC project plan should lay out elements in schedules, resources, and personnel. Estimating supplies in the budget, cost monitoring and control ahead can ensure the continuity of a project. It is necessary to clarify the evaluation methods and to report, especially the identification of the predecessor and successor relationships^[9]. Finally, the project plan should include potential problems and risk controls.

People and Knowledge are essential: Information Technology projects are incredibly abstract because of balance among software, human beings and the computer system^[8]. BBC lack knowledge to successfully execute a project and embark on a project of this nature without the technical certainty. The missing of a senior responsible owner (SRO) from business leads BBC DMI to an emphasis on technological aspects of the programme rather than the complete change for the organization^[2].

Phase III: Execution

Not every project is suited for Agile Software Development: The revised project of DMI utilized Agile Software Development, which has become fashionable to describe new approaches that focus on the close collaboration between programming teams and business experts. However, agile makes sense for some project, not all. The agile development agreed upfront did not develop the whole system end to end^[8]. Requirements for Agile Software Development is flexible and emerges throughout the event, resulting in the potential scope creep and less predictability to DMI. The barriers to software vision and conflicts in time controls make DMI break down at the near end period.

The meeting is critical in implementation: The team should conduct a high-quality meeting because it is the efficient way to develop a mutual trust, to collaborate on strategies, plannings, creativities, and to communicate efficiently^[8]. A high-quality meeting is more comfortable for a team to analyze and solve problems because everyone has to hear the same information and gets a chance to influence the decision. Apart from above mentioned benefits, celebrations of milestones in the meeting could build the team moral quickly^[9]. If DMI conducted and updated

period meetings during the whole project process, the gap in business and technology would be reduced step and step.

Phase IV: Delivery

Different results for different periods: The purpose of project delivery is project assessments, completion certainty, lessons learnings and practical application to future projects^[9]. Project sponsors should understand outputs for short-term, outcomes for mid-term and impacts for long-term when refining projects in delivery period. Project goals, objectives, Scope, and Technology should be consistent for all project stakeholders if the project is to be successful in meeting all of their expectations and avoiding scope creep^[8].

7.0 Recommendation- Lingyi Meng

7.1 Professional Manager Team

For a project to success, the credentialed professional project managers are necessary because project managers play a role in balancing between integrative PM and technology specialization, with emphasis on experience in successful integrative Project Management^[10]. DMI should attain consistently successful project delivery across multiple Project Managers because the PM infrastructure needs to be centralized. DMI should ensure experienced senior managers to take on any project and managers to manage ever-larger and complex integrative projects^[8].

7.2 Information Gathering In Advance

To start a project, you need information. How to gather sufficient and appropriate information is the key. Here we can follow the four steps to ensure what we collect is of integrity:

- **Step one:** Refer project archives within the company to obtain any relevant information from other projects and build benchmark requirements data.
- **Step two:** Develop technical specifications based on stakeholder/customer map for a clear scope.
- **Step three:** Identify human resource needs and match needs with availabilities.
- **Step four:** Determine organizational structure of the team, including role assignment and senior management endorsement^[10].

7.3 Learn From History

The PM organization should look at aspects of its processes, infrastructure, and environment to figure out what in the past has been successful and the reason for that and the differences between current projects and the situation. Also, DMI need to understand, leverage and manage the advances in software and changes in an interpersonal relationship in projects. In the delivery phase, the team should document processes and lessons learned and understand the development of the overall profession. At the same time, search for qualified personnel and professional paths^[10].

7.4 Enforce Learning Process

The organization should embed formalized training and informal knowledge sharing among members. Information or knowledge could transfer through Top-down method, in which management plays the crucial role in shifting both tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge^[8]. At the same time, implicit and explicit knowledge could transfer from middle managers and self-organizing teams through Middle-up-down method^[10].

7.5 Manage Agile PM Methods

A framework for deploying Agile Methods provides a prescriptive guideline for DMI to control Agile. Change is constant, DMI must have adequate, transparent and timely communication for employees to understand Agile better^[3]. All activities must contribute measurable value regarding the simplest solution. Make sure period feedback to keep optimism in sensible checks. Also, courage is necessary to deal with consequences of change. All stakeholders and participants have a responsibility to contribute to the greater whole because project managers can even make a mistake. Rapid and flexible modifications are necessary for the team to build an efficient Agile Software Delivery Process. Applying Agile Principles in practice should enable agility, incremental changes to the requirements, system project plan and artifacts results. Finally, a working software system is the primary goal of Agile Methods^[2].

7.6 Make a Planning Checklist for project plan

Planning Checklist could help DMI figure out what the project supposed to do, what are the mission, goals, and objectives precisely and how to organize and staff the project, at least for the

initial steps. DMI should make a organized list of the tasks to accomplish the project, layout these functions on a preliminary schedule, estimate the resources required to do each one of the tasks and identify the predecessor and successor relationships for each job. In order to emphasize what activities are necessary to meet the specifications in the project definition, DMI should prepare Work Breakdown Structure (WBS). WBS is a core project deliverable that organizes the team's work into manageable sections. WBS starts with the project as the top level deliverable and is further decomposed into sub-deliverables using outline hierarchy, which understandably conducts the project^[12]. For BBC DMI, the budget can be allocated to the top levels of the WBS and department budgets can be quickly calculated based on the each project's WBS^[20].

8.0 Conclusion - Sarath Laghumarapu

BBC's Digital Media Initiative project failed completely and was eventually scrapped. They did several things wrong from the inception of the project. The project cost £98.4m and five years of development with almost no results to show^[13]. If one main reason can be pointed out for the project failure it would be BBC's complacency. They did not put in the effort to understand the risks involved in completing this complex project. Through DMI, BBC wanted to transform itself into a more digital savvy company and integrate latest technologies. To achieve this, they wanted to create a new database which will act as a digital library for its programmes, new software tools for content creation and editing and an enterprise system connecting everything together. This project was supposed to be adopted throughout the BBC to make it more efficient and make employees of BBC more productive.

The original vision of one overarching, all encompassing, one-size-fits-all digital solution for video archiving and editing across the entire BBC was probably over-optimistic – in both technical and cultural terms^[14]. So, we could see that the BBC was not clear about its objectives from the beginning and underestimated the complexity of the project. BBC selected Siemens for implementing the project without conducting effective tendering process. BBC should have conducted a proper tendering process and selected the company which had a detailed plan of execution with least budget. Also, Siemens was given a fixed price contract and upon reflection this was a bad idea as this arrangement probably discouraged BBC from getting too deeply involved in the design stages for fear of triggering change requests thereby nullifying the fixed price.

Even though Siemens was awarded the contract there was no oversight committee in BBC accountable for the project. Because of this no one was aware of what was happening in the project and eventually when it was determined that no progress was made in one year, Siemens was taken out of the project. This shows that fixed price contract is not a good option if the user requirements are not clearly defined beforehand even though buyer is safeguarded from cost overruns in this type of contract. In 2009, the project is moved internally but BBC has not taken sufficient steps to learn from their mistakes with Siemens and failed to do proper risk and scope assessment.

Problems continued even with the development of the project in house. Lack of an overarching committee in charge of the project led to internal politics between technology department and business users. Technology team believed the software was making the progress as per the initial vision, but the users never brought into the original vision and kept changing business

requirements. Also, hierarchical structure of organization and failure to set up proper communication flows led to green shifting^[15], where employees failed to intimate their seniors the shortcomings of the project and kept giving them positive information. There was no proper schedule of meeting for monitoring the project and this led to a delay in the flow of information. This is an example of failure of stakeholder management or proper monitoring and controlling.

So eventually the project was scrapped as the costs kept increasing with no results to show. We can see from our analysis that DMI project by BBC failed in the five essential components for a successful project management – Scope management, Risk management, Stakeholder management, Communications management, and Schedule management. We believe that if BBC had followed our six main recommendations - employ a professional manager team, gather information in advance, learn from their previous projects, manage Agile PM methods and proper planning, the project would have been successful.

Appendix

Figure 1^[1]

Summary of events

The BBC established the Programme in October 2006 and cancelled it in May 2013

Source: National Audit Office based on various published and unpublished sources provided

Figure 2^[12]

Group	DMI meeting frequency	Role
Executive Board	Quarterly	Responsible for operational management of the BBC and for the delivery of BBC services according to the plans that have been agreed with the Trust.
DG Finance Committee	Quarterly	Responsible for reviewing and approving investment cases and monitoring spend and benefits.
BDG	As required	Responsible for managing pan-BBC issues delegated to it from the Executive Board and ensuring that the organisation meets its pan-BBC objectives.
DMI Steering Group	Monthly	To guide and direct DMI to deliver the outcomes and vision outlined in the benefits and business case approved by the BBC Executive and the Trust. To ensure continued alignment of DMI with business direction and editorial strategy.
Technical Quality Group	Monthly	To support the DMI programme in ensuring that it follows best practices in technical delivery, that the solution is aligned with the FM&T strategy and that data integrity is maintained.
Programme Leadership Meeting	Weekly	To guide and direct the programme to ensure it delivers the desired outcomes and benefits in the required timescales.
Deployment and Change Group (DCG)	Every 2 weeks	With the support of the DMI Business Requirements Delivery Team, to enable local-level benefits realisation through effective deployment, roll-out and use of Fabric. To include: maintaining a co-ordinated change plan and ensuring business readiness.
Delivery Meeting	Weekly	Responsible for the day-to-day running of the DMI workstreams.

Figure 3^[1]

Staffing changes

Discontinuity in key programme roles

Figure 4^[1]

Quarterly changes in the DMI risk rating reported by the project management office to the BBC executive board and the BBC Trust finance committee

The BBC's executive board and the Trust finance committee did not receive timely information on increases to the Programme's risk rating

Date	Risk rating	Number of days after quarter end the executive board received the report	Number of days after quarter end the Trust finance committee received the report
Jan to Mar 2010	Amber	75	99
Apr to Jun 2010	Amber	75	99
Jul to Sep 2010	Amber	67	105
Oct to Dec 2010	Amber	66	97
Jan to Mar 2011	Amber	74	98
Apr to Jun 2011	Amber-Red	74	70
Jul to Sep 2011	Amber-Red	66	62
Oct to Dec 2011	Red	Not received	Not received
Jan to Mar 2012	Red	72	96
Apr to Jun 2012	Red	72	96
Jul to Sep 2012	Red	43	67
Oct to Dec 2012	Red	70	65
Jan to Mar 2013	Red	43	76

Figure 5^[16]

Figure 6^[17]

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